

Shining Bright at 960 nm: A 28-Silver-Atom Nanorod Stabilized by DNA

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Fluorescence imaging is a key tool in biological and medical sciences. Despite the potential for increased imaging depth in the near-infrared range, the limited availability of bright emitters hinders its widespread implementation. In this work, a DNA-stabilized silver nanocluster (DNA–AgNC) with bright emission at 960 nm in solution is presented, which redshifts further to 1055 nm in the solid and crystalline states. The atomic structure, composition and charge of this DNA–AgNC are determined by combining single-crystal X-ray diffraction and electrospray ionization–mass spectrometry. This unique atomically precise silver nanocluster consists of 28 silver atoms, of which are neutral (Ag_{28}^{16+}), arranged in a rodlike shape, and measures just over 2 nm in length. Interestingly, differences are observed in the number of chlorido ligands between the solution and crystalline states, highlighting the important but not yet fully understood role of chlorides in fine-tuning the optical properties of this class of emitters. The structure of this silver nanorod, along with the fully characterized photophysical properties, represents a cornerstone for understanding the intricate interactions between silver and DNA bases, as well as paving the way for the rational design of the next-generation imaging probes.

increased tissue transparency due to reduced light scatter and absorption, while on the other hand, the small bandgap increasingly favors non-radiative decay pathways over fluorescence. As a result, only a limited number of bright emitters are available in the NIR region.^[1] To date, only two fluorophores—indocyanine green (ICG) and methylene blue (MB)—have been approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for use in intraoperative imaging.^[2] The ideal NIR emitter should be bright, relatively small, compatible with biological media, nontoxic, and functionalizable. A relatively new class of emitters known as DNA-stabilized silver nanoclusters (DNA–AgNCs) can meet these aforementioned requirements.^[3–5] DNA–AgNCs comprise a limited number of silver atoms and cations (<30) templated by one or more single-stranded DNA oligomers.^[6–12] The DNA acts as a genome that steers the final chemical outcome of

1. Introduction

The near-infrared (NIR) region has a double-edged nature when it comes to fluorescence imaging. On the one hand, it offers

the silver nanoclusters, with atomic precision.^[5] The heavy nature of silver atoms (as compared to e.g., carbon) and hence the low vibrational bond frequencies have allowed DNA–AgNCs to maintain high brightness in the NIR I range (≈ 700 – 1000 nm),^[3,13] and, in recent years, attention has started to shift toward the NIR II (1000–1700 nm) region. Copp et al. employed machine learning tools to discover DNA–AgNCs with emission maxima in the NIR II window,^[14] and Liisberg et al. demonstrated the feasibility of performing single-molecule imaging and spectroscopy of DNA–AgNCs emitting at the NIR I/II border.^[13]

To further expand the palette of NIR-emitting DNA–AgNCs, there is a strong need to determine the exact structure of these materials. Indeed, since their discovery in 2004,^[15] only two full structures and a partial one have been reported.^[16–18] The lack of DNA–AgNC structures hampers the understanding of the interaction between DNA bases and silver, preventing the rational design of DNA sequences for DNA–AgNCs with tailored optical properties. For example, knowing the structure of $\text{DNA}_2[\text{Ag}_{16}\text{Cl}_2]^{8+}$ allowed Cerretani et al. to reengineer the DNA sequence by replacing guanosines with inosines, resulting in a quantum yield improvement and lengthening of decay time without affecting absorption and emission maxima.^[19] Moreover, the paucity of structures prevents the possibility of performing electronic structure calculations that might aid in understanding the

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origin of the unusual large Stokes shifts,^[20,21] and the electronic nature of the emissive states.^[22] Additionally, knowing the exact structure of these emitters supports targeted engineering for bio-conjugation strategies. For instance, the study by Rück et al. relied on the structural knowledge of DNA₂[Ag₁₆Cl₂]⁸⁺ to attach a reactive group to the DNA strands, enabling its application in cellular imaging.^[23] Ultimately, these examples prove the importance of obtaining structures of DNA–AgNCs to develop tailored NIR emitters.

Here we present an atomically precise AgNC consisting of 28 silver atoms shaped as a rod, with two chlorido ligands in the crystalline state. The main AgNC-related absorption is situated at 835 nm and its emission spans the NIR I/II border region, peaking at 960 nm in solution. A high brightness of 25 200 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹—calculated as the product of a molar absorption coefficient of 210 000 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and a fluorescence quantum yield of 0.12—was achieved. Electrospray ionization–mass spectrometry (ESI–MS) and single-crystal X-ray diffraction allowed to obtain both compositional and structural information of this fluorophore. This NIR-emissive DNA–AgNC is the longest atomically precise silver nanorod, whose structure has been solved so far; hence, it constitutes the cornerstone for furthering the research and discovery of DNA–AgNCs emitting even deeper in the NIR II region.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Steady-State and Time-Resolved Properties

The DNA–AgNC presented here was synthesized using the single-stranded DNA sequence 5'-CCGCGCGCGCCGCGAA-3'. This DNA sequence was part of a larger set of 16-base sequences designed by Copp et al.^[24] to stabilize AgNCs that emit between 600 and 660 nm. However, by optimizing synthesis conditions and formation time, a different and bright NIR-emissive DNA–AgNC was obtained. The optimal ratio [DNA]:[AgNO₃]:[NaBH₄] was determined to be 30:240:240 μM. The DNA–AgNC was synthesized in either 10 mM or 50 mM ammonium acetate (NH₄OAc), with a better yield of formation in the latter case. High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) purification was performed after 5 days to maximize the yield of the desired product. Detailed synthesis and purification methods are provided in the Supporting Information.

Figure 1A shows that the doubly HPLC-purified sample has an absorption maximum at 835 nm and an emission maximum centered at 960 nm, resulting in a Stokes shift of 1559 cm⁻¹. The fluorescence quantum yield was determined to be 12%, using a previously characterized DNA–AgNC with an 830 nm emission as a reference (see Supporting Information for details). Additionally, we found a molar absorption coefficient of 210 000 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (at 835 nm) employing a recently developed method.^[25] The resulting brightness, calculated by multiplying the molar absorption coefficient by the quantum yield, is 25 200 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹. This value is significantly larger than that of the FDA-approved ICG and MB (see Table S2, Supporting Information). Time-correlated single photon counting measurements were performed exciting at 790 nm, and an intensity-weighted average decay time $\langle \tau \rangle$ of 0.65 ns was obtained.

Figure 1. A) Normalized absorption and emission spectra ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 790$ nm) of the 960 nm emissive DNA–AgNC in 50 mM ammonium acetate measured at room temperature. B) Decay curve (light green) of the emission, measured with an 815 nm long pass filter, exciting at 790 nm. The instrument response function (IRF) is reported in gray, while the dashed green curve is the tri-exponential reconvolution function used to fit the fluorescence decay. The individual amplitudes and decay time components can be found in Table S1, Supporting Information.

Details on the measurements and data analysis are reported in Supplementary Information. Excitation anisotropy measurements, monitoring the emission at 850 nm, yielded a value of 0.35 (Figure S8, Supporting Information), which is close to 0.4, indicating almost parallel absorption and emission transition dipole moments.

To obtain structural information, single crystals up to ≈ 100 μm in length were grown, enabling successful X-ray diffraction measurements (*vide infra*). Furthermore, to confirm that the structure obtained from the crystallographic data is representative of the solution state, emission spectra and fluorescence decay times were recorded for several crystals. The emission spectra shown in Figure S5, Supporting Information, reveal that the emission maximum is redshifted about 95 nm with respect to the solution, while the decay time is shorter, ranging from 0.16 to 0.23 ns, depending on the crystal. The similar nanosecond decay times for both the solution and the crystalline state indicate that the emissive states have alike allowed transition character. Differences between the emission spectra of the crystalline and solution states have been previously observed for other DNA–AgNCs and are likely due to a combination of additional chlorido ligands, different hydration levels in the two states, and crystal packing interactions.^[26,27]

To check the hydration effect, we measured the emission spectrum of a droplet of our DNA–AgNC solution, before and after evaporation of water. Figure S6, Supporting Information, shows that the spectrum of the dried-out droplet is similar to the crystal

spectrum, both being redshifted by ≈ 95 nm to a maximum around 1055 nm, now clearly located in the NIR II region. Furthermore, the presence of additional chlorido ligands in the crystalline state might also play a big role in the redshift of the emission spectrum (*vide infra*). Further follow-up experiments and theoretical calculations could help to shed light on the observed shift.

2.2. Structural Characterization

Crystals of the HPLC-purified 960 nm emissive DNA–AgNC were grown using the hanging drop vapor diffusion method in an environment containing 50 mM 3-(N-morpholino)propanesulfonic acid (pH 7), 10 mM spermine, a NO_3^- salt at various concentrations, and 10% 2-methyl-2,4-pentanediol or polyethylene glycol 3350 at 293 K.^[17,18] Details on the crystallization conditions are provided in Supplementary Information. **Figure 2A** shows an example of a crystal captured in a CryoLoop ($\approx 160 \times 20 \times 15$ μm). The crystal structure is shown in **Figure 2B**. The atomic coordinates and experimental data have been deposited in the Protein Data Bank (PDB) with the accession code 9KHW. The space group is $P2_1$, indicating a monoclinic crystal with lattice parameters $a = 27.2$ \AA , $b = 53.2$ \AA ,

$c = 27.2$ \AA , and $\beta = 103.7^\circ$. The asymmetric unit of this crystal is composed of one $\text{DNA}_2\text{--}[\text{Ag}_{28}\text{Cl}_2]^{14+}$. The 28 silvers forming the cluster are organized in a twisted, rodlike configuration (**Figure 2B**). The confined Ag_{28} cluster (**Figure 2C**) is 21.4 \AA in length and 3.9 \AA in diameter, yielding an aspect ratio of 5.5. Each DNA strand wraps around one-half of the AgNC rod, with all nucleobases except C_8 interacting with the silver atoms. Interestingly, two chlorido ligands are bound to the cluster, similarly to the previously determined $\text{DNA}_2\text{--}[\text{Ag}_{16}\text{Cl}_2]^{8+}$ structure.^[28] The detection of chlorido ligands is particularly noteworthy, as no chloride was deliberately added during the synthesis, purification, and crystal growth. This means that it must originate from impurities in the used chemicals and solvents, as chlorido ligands were also observed in other cluster compounds.^[28–30]

To simplify the complex arrangement of silvers within the Ag_{28} rod, we distinguished three arbitrary sections (I, II, and III, **Figure 2C**). At both ends, the silvers are arranged in two edge-sharing octahedra (yellow-dashed lines), whereas in the middle part, the silver atoms are organized into two tetrahedra (red dashed lines). The tetrahedral and octahedral segments are linked in a manner that appears disordered at first glance, but can be also seen as two distorted trigonal bipyramid

Figure 2. A) Single crystal of $\text{DNA}_2\text{--}[\text{Ag}_{28}\text{Cl}_2]^{14+}$ mounted in a CryoLoop. The crystal was grown in 3-(N-morpholino)propanesulfonic acid (pH 7), 10 mM spermine, 300 mM NaNO_3 , and 10% 2-methyl-2,4-pentanediol at room temperature. B) Structure determined from single crystal X-ray diffraction of a crystal grown in 3-(N-morpholino)propanesulfonic acid (pH 7), 10 mM spermine, 10 mM $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, and 10% 2-methyl-2,4-pentanediol at room temperature. The two DNA strands have their carbon atoms colored in green and blue, and the silver atoms are represented by gray spheres, while the chlorido ligands are shown as green spheres. C) Side view of Ag_{28}^{16+} (gray spheres) and two chlorido ligands (green spheres), with highlighted Ag–Ag bonds (< 3.40 \AA) represented by dashed lines. The color coding of the lines is only used to facilitate the description of the overall cluster. The segments indicated with I, II, and III are those discussed in the text and described in **Figure 3A,B**, **Figure 3C,D**, and **Figure 3E,F**, respectively.

configurations (blue-dashed lines). The Ag–Ag bond distances range from 2.6 Å, shorter than their metallic radii, to 3.4 Å, a value close to the sum of their van der Waals radii (Figure S10, Supporting Information). Observation of bond lengths below 2.88 Å is consistent with the tendency of metallic bond distances to be shorter in clusters compared to bulk metals.^[17,31]

To further describe the coordinate bonds between silver atoms and DNA nucleobases, DNA₂–[Ag₂₈Cl₂]¹⁴⁺ was divided into three sections corresponding to the two edge-sharing octahedra and one tetrahedron, as shown in Figure 2C. Only one-half of the structure is discussed, as the other half presents the same interactions between silvers and nucleobases. All cytosines, but C₈, interact with two silvers at a time *via* N3 and O2, where O2 is the oxygen bound to C2. We note that for all Ag–O interactions described here, we have considered distances up to 2.8 Å. Figure 3A,B illustrates the coordination bonds of the silver atoms belonging to the outermost octahedron. These six silver atoms are stabilized by 8 DNA nucleobases—G₃, G₁₂, C₁₁, C₁₃, C₄, C₂, C₁₀, and G₁₄—four of which (C₄, C₂, C₁₀, and G₁₄) are shared with the adjacent octahedron. G₁₂ interacts with two silvers *via* N7 and O6 (the oxygen bound to C6), whereas G₃ forms only one coordinate bond *via* N7. G₁₄ and C₁₀ interact with the same silver shared with the adjacent octahedron through O6 and N3, respectively, while C₄ and C₂ bind the other shared silver *via* N3 and O2, respectively. C₁₁ and C₁₃

interact with the same silver atom through O2 and N3, respectively. In addition, C₁₀ and C₁₁ coordinate the same silver *via* the binding site not involved in the previously described interactions. C₂ and C₁₃ interact, respectively, through N3 and O2 with the atom at the other vertex of the octahedron. Figure 3C,D shows the interactions of the silver atoms that are part of the second octahedron. G₁₄ and C₁ coordinate the same silver atom *via* N1 and O2, respectively, where the N1 of the guanine is deprotonated. Furthermore, C₁ interacts with a second silver through N3. G₅ stabilizes two silvers *via* N7 and O6; while A₁₅ coordinates one silver atom through N1. G₉ interacts *via* O6 with one silver of the octahedron and through the deprotonated N1 with one silver of the neighboring tetrahedron (Figure 3E,F). Deprotonated N1s of guanines have been also observed in the structure of DNA₂–[Ag₁₆Cl₂]⁸⁺ and its mutations thereof.

Figure 3E,F reports the interactions within the tetrahedral segment. G₇ forms two coordinate bonds with two silvers *via* N7 and O6, while A₁₆ interacts through N1 with one silver atom. Two other silvers are instead coordinated by O2 and N3 of C₆. One of the silvers in this section is also bound to a chlorido ligand, similarly to the structure of DNA₂–[Ag₁₆Cl₂]⁸⁺. In addition, the chloride anion makes a Cl···H–N hydrogen bond with the amino group at the N4 position of the C₆ base. An important role in encapsulating the AgNC is also provided by silver-mediated quartets, such as Ag-mediated C₂–C₄–C₁₁–C₁₃ and C₁–G₅–C₁₀–G₁₄, which are stabilized by N4(C)–H···O6(G) and N2(G)–H···O2(C) hydrogen bonds (Figure S11, Supporting Information). The bond distances for Ag–N are between 2.2 and 2.4 Å, whereas Ag–O bond lengths span from 2.2 to 2.8 Å (Figure S10, Supporting Information).

Finally, the two chlorides are bound to two silvers each, with one distance being 2.6 Å and the other 2.8 Å (Figure S10, Supporting Information). Moving from the coordinate bonds between silvers and DNA nucleobases to the sole interactions among nucleobases, it is worth noting the hydrogen bonds formed between the hydroxyl group at 5' of C₁ and the oxygen of the C₈ phosphate group. These hydrogen bonds are key in bridging the two stabilizing DNA strands, allowing for the formation of the AgNC rod (Figure S12, Supporting Information). Crystal packing interactions are then promoted by Watson–Crick G₃–C₈ base pair formation.

Another interesting aspect is the chirality of the DNA strands. C₁, C₂, and G₃, where G₃ takes a *syn* conformation, are left-handed, like the Z-form of DNA, while both segments before (C₄–G₅–C₆–G₇) and after (G₉–C₁₀) C₈ are right-handed. C₂–G₃–C₄ and C₁₁–G₁₂–C₁₃ form instead hairpin loops.

2.3. Compositional Characterization

X-ray diffraction data unraveled the structure and composition of the 960 nm emissive DNA–AgNC but did not provide information regarding the cluster's charge. To address this, ESI–MS was employed. The HPLC-purified sample, prepared in 50 mM NH₄OAc, was directly injected into a mass spectrometer. The mass spectrum, recorded in negative ion mode, is presented in Figure 4A (see Supporting Information for details on ESI–MS measurements and data analysis). We identified two peaks at *m/z* 2541.144 and 2117.468 for *z* = 5[–] and *z* = 6[–],

Figure 3. Cross sections of DNA₂–[Ag₂₈Cl₂]¹⁴⁺ corresponding to the segments I, II, and III given in Figure 2C. A,B) Side and front view of segment I—outermost octahedron, C,D) side and front view of segment II—neighboring edge-sharing octahedron, and E,F) side and front view of segment III—middle part of the Ag₂₈ cluster.

Figure 4. A) Mass spectrum of the 960 nm emissive DNA–AgNC in 50 mM ammonium acetate. Below m/z 2110, only fragments are present. B) Zoomed-in view of the molecular ion peak with $z = 6^-$ charge state. The experimental isotopic distribution is reported (blue) together with the theoretical isotopic distribution (light green). The calculated average mass is m/z 2117.468, which corresponds to $C_{304}H_{386}N_{128}O_{184}P_{30}[Ag_{28}]^{16+}$. The zoomed-in view of the molecular ion peak with $z = 5^-$ charge state can be found in Figure S12, Supporting Information.

respectively, corresponding to an experimental mass of $12710.512 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$. This value is consistent with the crystalline structure with the exception of the two chlorido ligands. This means that the DNA–AgNC is formed by two DNA strands and 28 silver atoms ($N = 28$), of which 12 are reduced ($N_0 = 12$), resulting in an overall charge of 16^+ . This is in line with the “magic” number of metallic silvers predicted by Copp et al. for rodlike NIR-emitting DNA–AgNCs.^[32] Even numbers of $N_0 = 4$ and $N_0 = 6$ were indeed found to corresponded to green- and red-emission DNA–AgNCs, respectively, while NIR emitters are characterized by $N_0 = 10$ or 12 .^[32] Hence, the Ag_{28} nanocluster has a charge of 16^+ . Overall, assuming all phosphates are fully protonated, the chemical formula can be written as $C_{304}H_{386}N_{128}O_{184}P_{30}[Ag_{28}]^{16+}$. The neutral species in the mass spectrometry data corresponds to $C_{304}H_{370}N_{128}O_{184}P_{30}Ag_{28}$.

Further analysis of the mass spectrum revealed the presence of a Cl^- adduct, $DNA_2-[Ag_{28}Cl]^{15+}$, observed at m/z 2123.479 for $z = 6^-$, and a less well-defined peak at m/z 2133.645, for $z = 6^-$, corresponding to $NaCl_2^-$ adduct (Figure S15–S17, Supporting Information). Unlike for the previously reported NIR-emissive $DNA_2-[Ag_{16}Cl_2]^{8+}$, where the two chlorido ligands were observed in both mass spectrometry and single-crystal X-ray diffraction data,^[28] the 960 nm emitter presents some differences in the number of chloride ions between the solution and crystalline state (see Supporting Information for additional details and spectra).

To investigate if this difference is due to up-concentration effects of chloride anions when crystals are formed, we decided to add an excess of NaCl (≈ 119 times higher than that of the DNA–AgNC concentration). As shown in Figure S19, Supporting Information, upon NaCl addition, a minor redshift of the absorption maximum of about 10 nm is observed and the chemical stability is not significantly affected. Intriguingly, the Cl^- adduct, $DNA_2-[Ag_{28}Cl]^{15+}$, becomes the base peak in the mass spectrum (Figure S15–S17, Supporting Information), while the peak related to the original $DNA_2-[Ag_{28}]^{16+}$ is extremely reduced (Figure S16, Supporting Information). Once again, only a small peak related to the $NaCl_2^-$ adduct is present, but no clear peak corresponding to $DNA_2-[Ag_{28}Cl_2]^{14+}$ can be found.

While it is plausible that even higher concentrations of NaCl are needed to form $DNA_2-[Ag_{28}Cl_2]^{14+}$ in solution, we speculate that the di-chlorido compound is preferably assembled in the crystalline state.

Figure S13, Supporting Information, shows that the electron densities next to the Ag_{28} cluster are best assigned to chlorines. To further confirm this, energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) measurements were performed on multiple positions of the crystal used for structure determination (Figure 5A). As expected, the

Figure 5. A) Scanning electron microscope (SEM) image of the $DNA_2-[Ag_{28}Cl_2]^{14+}$ crystal used for structure determination. The crystal was transferred from the CryoLoop to the carbon tape and imaged with SEM. B) EDX spectra from different positions on the crystal. EDX confirmed the presence of chlorine in the crystal. EDX spectra, normalized to the Ag peak at 3.0 keV, can be found in Figure S20, Supporting Information.

acquired EDX spectra (Figure 5B) show the presence of silver, phosphorus, carbon, nitrogen, and oxygen and confirm the presence of chlorine. Sulfur was also detected because of the 3-(*N*-morpholino)propanesulfonic acid buffer used in the crystallization process. The EDX spectra additionally revealed the presence of common alkali and alkaline earth metals, such as calcium (due to the nitrate salt used for crystallization), magnesium, sodium, and potassium. Interestingly, the latter two cations are also commonly observed in the ESI-MS data of DNA-AgNCs.

3. Conclusion

We reported an atomically precise silver nanorod composed of 28 silver atoms stabilized by two 16-base DNA strands and two additional chlorido ligands in the crystalline state. Each strand stabilizes one-half of the structure. The N_0 value of 12 leads to an emission band that spans the NIR I/II border region, with a maximum at around 960 nm in solution. When dried and in the crystalline state, the emission peak further redshifts to 1055 nm. Furthermore, a brightness of $25\,200\text{ M}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was achieved, outcompeting the current FDA-approved dyes. Composition, charge and structure of this new fluorophore were elucidated through ESI-MS and single-crystal X-ray diffraction. Intriguing differences between these two techniques point toward the ability of the Ag₂₈ nanorod to acquire two chlorido ligands in certain conditions. This NIR-emitting DNA-AgNC represents the longest atomically precise silver nanorod characterized to date, paving the way for understanding the structure-photophysical property relationship of DNA-AgNCs and designing the next generation of fluorophores with emission in the NIR II region.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Giacomo Romolini: data curation (equal); formal analysis (equal); investigation (equal); writing—original draft (equal); and writing—review editing (equal). **Hiroki Kanazawa**: data curation (equal); investigation (equal); writing—original draft (supporting); and writing—review editing (supporting). **Christian Brinch Mollerup**: investigation (supporting); writing—original draft (supporting); and writing—review editing (supporting). **Mikkel Baldtzer Liisberg**: formal analysis (supporting); investigation (supporting); writing—original draft (supporting); and writing—review editing (supporting). **Simon Wentzel Lind**: investigation (supporting) and writing—review editing (supporting). **Zhiyu Huang**: investigation (supporting) and writing—review editing (supporting). **Cecilia Cerretani**: formal analysis (equal); investigation (equal); supervision (equal); writing—original draft (equal); and writing—review editing (equal). **Jiro Kondo**: conceptualization (equal) and data curation (supporting). **Tom Vosch**: conceptualization (equal); supervision (equal); writing—original draft (equal); and writing—review editing (equal). **Giacomo Romolini** and **Hiroki Kanazawa** contributed equally to this work.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available in the supplementary material of this article and at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14846193>.

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